

Rights of African Traditional Religion Adherents and Eastern Ethnic Nationalities in the Political Manipulations of Nigeria Pluralistic Society

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Abstract

The three ethnic groups in Nigeria and seemingly three major religions were at the center of Nigeria polity shortly after independence of 1st October, 1960. To some peoples' surprises, the early Nigerian polity became later a showdown as Traditionalists and Eastern ethnic group are out of the game, being insufficiently involved at the federal level of government with their counterparts in Christianity and Islamic religion, Northern and Western regions respectably still involving. Hence, this study examines the possibility of holistic National and formal re-inclusion of African Traditional Religion adherents and Eastern ethnical cultural region in the Nigerian Polity of Nigerian pluralistic society. This as well stands as the lacuna in existing studies that this study fills. The methodology adopted is both phenomenological and historical. It is historical because "to understand Nigerian society, one must understand the role of religion in it with the sense of history". The result holds that Nigeria is neither a religious state nor for any ethnic group to usurp authority at the expense of others. Rather, it is a pluralistic state where every citizenry regardless of his or her religious or ethnic affiliation has equal right to vote for and be voted for. This study thereby is significant in making African Traditional Religion and Eastern ethnic region count in the holistic administration of the Nation. Recommendations are proffered to different religious and ethnic religious stakeholders that each religion and ethnic region be allowed full participation in the administration of the country especially at the federal level for Nigeria's progress and development

Keywords: Religion, Ethnicity, African Traditional Religion (ATR), Islam, Christianity

Introduction

In Nigeria of today, politicking is a serious business and partakers thereof are Nigeria citizens from different ethnic groups and religious affiliations. However, ethnics' Chauvinism, nepotism, religious bigotry and discrimination had clouded Nigeria political space for a very long time. Nigeria as a pluralistic society suggests every group or religious affiliation has equal opportunity to contribute without denial to the progress and development of the country. It is of note that people of diverse cultures and races, also men from various religious backgrounds have their unique impacts in the progress of politics anywhere in the world. From and after independence in October 1st, 1960, each religion and ethnic group fights for power and also tries to retain, exercise and influences it over others since power is the centrality of politics. This plight and pursuit of power is quite important to ethnic or tribal groups and religious bodies because its acquisition determines the religion and ethnic group in the nation's control affairs. Since and after Nigeria 1960 independence, apathy among religious affiliations and tribal groupings became more glaring with some negative effects registering on the country's national development. Today the eastern group and African Traditional Religion, so to say, are sidelined in Nigeria federal National polity. It is therefore expedient for Nigeria Government to embrace in her Constitution equal recognition of all religious bodies and ethnic group for presidency. Also 'exclusive politics' of which certain group do exclude other ethnic groups during election should be discouraged in all its entirety by all ethnic groups in Nigeria.

For example, the 'exclusive politics' played by Chief Obafemi Awolowo both in the First and Second Republics made him to forfeit the winning the electoral post. In furtherance, it is right to say here that there is no

ethnic group who plays 'exclusive politics' and after all wins the presidency. Winning the presidency in the national political calculations of Nigeria can only be achieved through 'inclusive politics' in which all ethnic groups are welcomed without disparity. Abiola and Tinubu from the West won the presidency because they broke from Awolowo's 'exclusive politics' style and opted for 'inclusive politics'. Presidency is not offered to people. People calculated and fought for it. It would be seemly impossible for the East ethnic group to win the presidency if politics are played the way it is played. Collaboration of ethnic groups with one another (especially Eastern group with other groups in Nigeria) would afford winning the presidency; nobody dashes this esteemed Office out. It is won by a calculated effort. That's the fact.

In the meantime, the problem of unity or 'one Nigeria' started from the base. It was from the 'so called' founding founders of politics in Nigeria (though this seem not visible to many) due to their differences in political ideologies, inclinations, ethnic affinity and religions bigotries. The need to strike a balance in modern day Nigerian politics, calling forth a full participation of all political stakeholders from different ethnic groups and different religious groups in Nigeria, driving forth the nation, unite in fulfilling her mandate is the crux of this paper. It is the intention of this write-up to address the meaning of politics, Nigeria political space with religious and ethnical affiliation, effects of sidelining and discrimination, and possibly proffering a recommendation that will cater for the effect of disunity among religious bodies, ethnic and tribal groupings in a manner that is holistic and multi-perspective.

What is Politics?

The word politics has no univocal definition as it has been explained in different ways by different writers. However based on this paper, politics is derived from the Greek words '*polis*' meaning a city and from the word '*polls*' where comes the word *polites* translated as citizen.¹ The English word Politics is derived from the verb *polituo* which can mean to be a citizen, to govern a city or state, or administer the affairs of a state. Hence, politics can be seen as an act of governance, and could also be equally seen as a process of decision making both in private and public sphere. Also politics is a way of peace. Aristotle opined politics as the essence of social existence of two or more men interacting with one another. This may include national politics, municipal and international politics. Politics involve everybody and the use of political power. Some see politics as game which is played by its participants.²

Politics and Nigerians' Religious Affiliation

United States of America had her motto of nationalism to be "In God we Trust" showing some elements of religion. In Nigeria Nationalism as well, 'politics and religion' is held with extreme value despite her secularity nature. This is shown in the Nigeria second stanza of the National Anthem where a prayer is said on Nigeria's behalf while in the National Pledge, particularly in the last line of the pledge, a prayer- "so help me God" is prayed so as to live for what is professed.³ All these suggest that religion is an inescapable phenomenon in the politics of a nation. Nigeria, according to 1999 constitution is a secular state; however it is made up of people of different faith such as Islam, Christianity and African Traditional Religion among others.⁴ By the time Nigeria gained her independence in 1960, the country was drawn more or less along religions zones of influence. To this extent it has however been established by Nigerians that their country is a religious pluralistic society of three major religious groups. Muslims were large in numbers in the North and in the south majority are Christians. Over a long period of time, the traditional religion had been silenced or best to say operates underneath, probably due to her nature of accommodation and tolerance to other religions.

Persecution and criticism by other religious bodies had dotted the face of African Traditional Religion over a long period of time. However, Since African Traditional Religion is not a proselytizing religion and for her docility, the religion remains the recruiting grounds for other religious group. Although as said by many Nigeria citizens that there are three major religions practiced in Nigeria but in actual sense of it, two are well known, pronounced and recognized in the Nigeria political arena while the third which is African Traditional

Religion is rejected, unaccepted and un-announced at the presidential level of Nigeria government and probably at some other lower levels in the Nigeria Politics. Invariably, this attitude towards her personality lowers her personal esteem and morale towards the contributions of her quota or exercising her franchise in the nation's political Leadership. Her neglect of course negates the constitution act that says Nigeria is a pluralistic nation (though being secularist) in which every religion and tribe is at equilibrium, with no religion having autonomy, influence or control over others.

As it is earlier discussed, Nigeria is blessed with a triple religious heritage with members in multitude having different and fulfilling roles which are deeply rooted in their nature.⁵ This is summarized as follows: African Traditional Religion being the first religion in Nigeria is of the indigenous belief of majority of people in the earlier time however as of today, it is practised by few people compare with multitudes in the import religions of Islam and Christianity. It is a religion of crude behavior and experiences different from imported religion such as Christianity and Islam. African Traditional Religion being the oldest religious system in the country intimates Nigerian citizens or society with the power that resides in nature through which God interact with people.⁶ The doctrine of the religion is based on the five major structures viz-a-viz beliefs in Supreme Being, beliefs in divinities, beliefs in spirit, beliefs in ancestors, beliefs in magic and medicine.⁷

Christianity is another religion in Nigeria. It is the religion of the followers of Jesus Christ who believe salvation could only be sought through Jesus Christ whom they believed had died for the sin of the world. Christianity sees and recognizes God as ultimate power acknowledged through the power of the gospel.⁸ Islam however is the religion of the followers of Prophet Muhammad who are called Muslims. It is believed that God has chosen him as the last and seal of all prophets and messengers of God who can lead men to salvation and to the house of bliss on the Day of Judgment. Islam identifies devotion as a symbol of closeness to God and that society can maintain this closeness through devotion.⁹ It is germane to note that among the three religions practised in the country traditional religion is the least practised today because Islam and Christianity had fought hard to impose their cultures, beliefs and ways of life on her adherents.

Secularity of Nigeria States

Okeowo observed that despite Nigeria constitutional secularity, everything in Nigeria is either 'Christianised or Islamised', 'Westernised or Easternised' albeit colonialised. He submits that politically, everything in Nigeria is 'Religionised'.¹⁰ I questioned myself when will politics in Nigeria be Africanised, Indegenised or Nigerianised? Fatokun in support of Okeowo affirms that in some quarters, religion is a strong determining factor for who to vote for and who to refused. He said further that some Muslims from the North detest voting any political party if the leading contestant is not a Muslim. Some Muslim prefers to have their Muslim brother or sister in power so as to represent the interest of the Muslim community.¹¹ The Christians in some recent electoral processes in Nigeria had started behaving like wisely by trying to vote for Christian candidates like the Muslims in the Northern side of the country. Adogame in his reaction to the above attests that religion has assumed an enigmatic stance in Nigeria in a fashion that ethnic politics is almost being supplanted by religious politics.¹² However, the consequences of this political virus to the nations development is heinous and nothing than forming an unstable political nation void of peace, serenity and progress, only full of segregation, marginalization, rivalry, nepotism and apathy

Inferno of Major Two Religions in Nigeria and African Traditional Religion

Major two religions in Nigeria do not only arrogate to themselves the role of sole dispensers of salvation and canvassing for membership but also enjoin their followers to hate and kick against African Traditional Religion even abhor the personalities of its followers as if they are not human; as if members of Islam and Christianity were not previously members of African Traditional Religion and as if African Traditional Religion has no value at all in the development of the society. May I register here that most terrible war, killings and cruelty ever emerged came from religious crisis and originally most Nigeria religious inferno in the past started as a result of

Islam-Christian clashes before aggravating to inter-tribal or ethnic unrest. For Christians the catalyst for missionary zeal is derived from Mathew 28:19: “Go therefore and make disciples of all nations”. In Islam, passages such as Quran 9:29 says: “Fight against such as those who have been given the scriptures and believe not in Allah, nor the last day, who do not forbid what Allah and His apostles have forbidden, and do not embrace the true faith, until they pay tribute out of hand and utterly subdued.”

In carrying out these mandates, adherents of these religions have employed such means of politics of exclusion, intimidation, blackmailing, manipulation of ethnic sentiments and violence to outdo each other for ascendancy. Is it not what they do to African Traditional Religion coming back to them in the view of Law of Karma? Now the question is, “how is African Traditional Religion which is seen as bad in the public opinion not the same with Islam and Christianity from where comes inferno and wars that had claimed more lives than what men could imagined, with many citizens maimed and impoverished, properties lost and future crumbled? Some people are of claims that African Traditional Religion is barbaric, full of magic and charms to harm; but can we compare this with so much destruction of lives and properties that had been experienced on the platter of Islam-Christianity religious inferno?

The writer holds the right to raise up this point to disallow discrimination and bias that had dotted Nigerian religious sphere for too long and to clear from the mind of other religious groups that African Traditional Religion is not as bad as thought. In the actual fact, majority of people in political position who are equally members of Islam and Christianity cannot deny patronage to African Traditional religion (ATR) in times of crisis or turbulence of life and during election. In other words many people still make a patronage to this so called ‘abhorred and forgotten religion’-African Traditional Religion in times of trouble.

Although reality such as instant judgment from ATR-gods and misused of powers by some of ATR adherents cannot be swept under carpet. It is not in ATR alone this happens. It happens as well among the acclaimed ‘good religion’ of Islam and Christianity. The fact that ATR is fetish does not mean it is totally bad. Every religion has its bad and good side. So all religion should be welcomed since all point to one creator, the maker of heaven, earth, men and other creatures. It is therefore advisable for Nigerians not to vote and choose her leader based on religious belief or ethnic affinity but rather vote or choose his or her candidate base on good merit, good character, quality, ability and capability in various forms, somebody who they know is responsible enough to lead them regardless of religion, ethnic group or party. Therefore giving opportunity to African Traditional Religion adherents in the political ruling of the country should not pose anylonger a threat since what is sauce for the geese is sauce for the gander.

Tribal Nationalities and Political Manipulations in the Nigerian Political Space

The role played by tribalism and sectionalism in Nigerian Politics right from Independence is not all encouraging. Seemingly, all political behaviour has tribal and sectional undertones at all levels of political endeavor in Nigeria. Nigerians do not see themselves as one; for there is ethnic and sectional loyalty which has intrusion into Nigerian politics right from when Nigeria was divided into three regions: The Northern Region, The Western Region and The Eastern Region. Right from this time parties had been formed on ethnic considerations. During the first Republic for example the Action Group (AG) was the party of the South West, while Northern peoples’ Congress (NPC) was for the North and National Council of Nigerian Citizens (NCNC) was safeguarding the interest of the East. However the story about the formation of NCNC and the running of its affairs shows that Eastern group do not play ‘inclusive politics’ as earlier discussed in this piece, because the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons which was later changed to National Council of Nigerian Citizens was formed with the idea of political inclusiveness by a Yoruba Nationalist; Sir Herbert Macaulay before the party was made exclusive party of Eastern region by Nnamdi Azikiwe the Secretary-General of the party after the demise of Macaulay in 1948. Azikiwe ‘Ibonized’ the party and ran it exclusively while Yorubas had no longer roles or a part to play.

On this foundation of previous political party and styles in Nigeria, other contemporary political parties' ideologies and styles are built. Till today, the same pattern of sectionalism dot the face of Nigeria politics. No matter how nationalistic these parties are, they still have the elements of tribalism in their operations. People still vote on tribal and sectional lines. It is discovered that during elections in Nigeria, prime attention is given to politics of ethnics' chauvinism. Where this prevails, good and competent individuals may not emerge as candidates, let alone win elections. This development however, is explained in terms of immoral politics.¹³

Rights of People, Justice and Fairness in Distribution of Political Offices

There is no gainsaying to the fact that that the essence of life is to live and live comfortably. It is by this that man can contribute meaningfully to the development of his environment.¹⁴ But this is being denied because of the hostility and unfriendly environment as a result of various violations of rights of the people including deprivation of liberty for eastern nationalities and African Traditional Religion adherents to exercise their franchise in the national presidency position of the Nigeria politics.

What could be said to be the idea of right or human right can be traced to the theories of the early philosophers like Aristotle, Albert Dicey and Brocon. To Aristotle, human rights have a link with justice. According to him, Justice is the greatest of all virtues. He also defines it as what is fair and equal. Human rights according to him include providing an enablement for man to allow the best utilization of his God-given abilities.¹⁵ As to what happen in France in 1789, the revolutionaries stormed the Bastille, the prison house in Paris, to proclaim the declaration of rights of men and citizen. The efforts were to secure equality of the rights for all citizens. In 1776, Americans fought a war of independence in the pursuit of the right to live as free men of equal basic rights and opportunities. Eventually, George Washington incorporated modern basic human rights into law. The declaration states: "...that all men are created equal; that they are endowed by their creator with certain unalienable right that among those is life, liberty and the pursuit of happiness. That to secure rights, government is instituted among men, deriving their just power from the consent of the governed."

In Nigeria, the idea of freedom guarantee was first developed in 1958 at the constitution conference held in Lancaster House, London, in order to allay the fears of the minorities in the country. After the independence, the 1963 Republican constitution, described as home-grown Constitution, was made. It contained a comprehensive list of fundamental human rights. This comprehensive list was reproduced in the 1979 Constitutions. The provisions of this list are now in Chapter IV of the 1999 constitution.¹⁶ Sebiomo tries to explain human rights as those rights that are born with man and which a man enjoins for being a member of a society. The rights are God-given and ought not to be taken away or violated by any person or authority. These so called rights are universal and found in every culture and society. They are to be respected by all. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which was enacted in 1948, was for the prevention of inhuman treatment of man by man. It contains thirty (30) articles of human rights. The Human Rights as entrenched in chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria are;¹⁷

Section; 33-Right to life

Section; 34 Right to Dignity of Human Person

Section; 35 Right to Personal Liberty

Section; 36 Right to fair hearing

Section; 37 Right to Private and Family Life

Section; 38 Right to freedom of thought, conscience and Religion

Section; 39 Right to freedom of expression and the press

Section; 40 Right to peaceful assembly and association

Section; 41 Right to freedom of Movement

Section; 42 Right to freedom from discrimination

Section; 43 Right to acquire and own immovable property

Section; 44 Right to compulsory acquisition of property.¹⁸

In spite of the fact that these rights are entrenched in the constitution which everybody can have access to, the level at which government agencies, political bodies, ethnic groupings and individuals violate these rights with impunity is so alarming and has become a concern to both young and old in the country.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Injustice and corruption takes over when men are not given similar opportunities in a nation where her constitution dictates equal right for all men. Therefore this paper posits to Nigeria Government and politicians to ensure equal right for all citizens irrespective of their religions and ethnic groups, to vote or to be voted for. Tribalism and religion inclinations should not be the basis for selection into presidency but everybody should be allowed to participate without prejudice or bias. Government should maintain high standard of justice, striking equilibrium among religious groups and tribal or ethnic group, putting forth a strong measure that will prevent trespasses of any religious group and tribal groups in affecting badly the nations as a whole or opposing party or ethnic group. Government should endeavour to make all religions including African Traditional Religion and all ethnic groups including Eastern ethnic group count in Nigeria politics and that everybody in Nigeria should have the freedom of exerting his or her franchise at will not as forced or coerced.

Since power is the central concepts of politics and that is the bane of any politically inclined person, the electorate must entrust a worthy or credible persons into power of a nation regardless whether he is from their group or not. Deserving and worthy men whose past services were with proof of integrity, honesty, firm-rooted uprightness and justice are those who can lead Nigeria right. If trusted citizens were voted without consciousness of religious affiliations or ethnic groups, Nigeria would have maintained her good governance and serenity long time ago. As the problem in the country has always ensued on religious ground (especially among the so called notable religions in Nigeria) and the idea of ethnics' chauvinism in Nigeria political space, this paper thereby implores Nigerians to embrace all people in respect of their religions and ethnic groups in the election process into the presidency for a good leader Nigeria deserves without bias or prejudice.

Endnotes

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